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DELINEATION OF ECONOMIC AND ORGANIZATIONAL FACTORS IN MANAGING TOURISM BUSINESSES

The economic activity of tourism businesses, akin to any economic entity, is significantly influenced by the state of its internal (microenvironment), external (macroenvironment), and immediate (mesoenvironment) surroundings. To effectively operate in a dynamic environment, it is crucial to understand the key factors influencing the financial and economic activities of tourism businesses, develop decision-making mechanisms to address negative impacts, and leverage new economic situations for improving performance.

Distinguishing between economic and organizational factors is imperative as it allows for a nuanced understanding of how financial considerations and organizational strategies intersect and impact the overall functioning of tourism businesses.

Additionally, differentiating between these factors aids in crafting tailored management approaches that account for both economic variables and organizational dynamics, thereby enhancing the competitiveness and sustainability of tourism businesses in a rapidly evolving industry landscape.

For example, key factors in the macroenvironment impacting tourism businesses include political factors such as regulatory environment and stability, economic factors like overall economic situation and tax policies, and social factors such as demographic trends and consumer preferences. Ecological factors consider natural resources and environmental impacts, while technological factors involve technical progress and innovation policies. The international environment involves relations with international institutions and economic trends.

The economic management of tourism businesses necessitates strategic planning and the execution of plans over various time frames. This involves crafting strategies and tactics to optimize resource utilization, particularly in procurement and sales strategies. Planning, encompassing strategic, current, and operational aspects, alongside effective control mechanisms, serves as the primary lever of economic influence on management objects. The planning process involves setting goals, analyzing implementation methods, and resource provision, ultimately forming the foundation for budget formulation and successful operation within the tourism industry.

The operational plan of a tourism enterprise, particularly a tour operator, outlines tasks for creating a specified quantity, range, assortment, and quality of tourism products within a set timeframe based on orders or market demand. It involves using both natural and value indicators to determine the quantity of developed and implemented tourism packages, tours, or individual services. Additionally, various indicators are applied to evaluate establishments serving tourists, such as sleeping accommodations, dining capacity, seating capacity, and audience capacity. The performance of tourism businesses is assessed based on revenue generated from tourism services and goods. The feasibility of the tour product plan relies on resource provision and the availability of necessary production capacities.

In the tourism sector, there are various types of enterprises: some solely offer tourism services, while for others, tourism is just one aspect of their commercial activities. Those solely in tourism are termed primary service tourism businesses, while those deriving profit from other sources besides tourism are secondary service tourism businesses.

Primary services in the tourism industry include tour organizing and sales firms, hospitality establishments like hotels, motels, and camping sites, transportation companies catering to tourists, manufacturers of tourism-related goods, and retail businesses selling such goods. Specialization and labor cooperation are vital organizational forms in any industry within a market economy, including tourism, which can manifest as industry specialization, enterprise specialization, and internal enterprise specialization.

Industry specialization involves creating new enterprises for specific goods or services and dividing labor among industry entities. Business specialization focuses activities on specific products, services, or tasks. There are two main forms: product specialization, involving enterprises producing one type of product, and technological specialization, for those making materials and semi-finished products. The forms and importance of specialization vary by industry. Scientific and technical progress increases the need for specialized sectors in one product, complicating connections and requiring more cooperation.